

Analyst Administrator
Date Tuesday, May 17, 2022 12:02 PM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-116-2 crystals_1	Sample 026 By Administrator Date Tuesday, May 17 2022	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.